

Towards a Qualitative Paradigm: Rethinking Research and Researchers Assessment ReAss

CoARA Boost Cascade Funding – Call 1. Institutional Pilot (PI: Dr Montserrat Castelló)

Reformant l'avaluació de la recerca per afavorir la qualitat i l'impacte científic

Experiències i tendències en el marc de CoARA

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The Research Team

www.researcher-identity.com

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ReAss aims

**Pilot a reform of
research and
researcher
assessment practices**

Recognize diverse types of research contributions
Promote a broad consideration of research quality and societal impact,
Foster inclusivity, peer review, openness and collaboration among
researchers.

Additionally

To understand the challenges, biases and researchers' attitudes when
adopting new research assessment criteria
Reflect on the culture of research assessment developed over time in
the fields of education, communication, health and sports

Our initial work plan

Month 1-3:
Planning and
Resource
Allocation

Month 3-4:
Review of Current
Practices

Month 5-6:
Development of
New Criteria

Month 7-8:
Training and
Awareness
Raising

Month 9-10:
Implementation

Month 11:
Monitoring and
Feedback

Month 12:
Evaluation and
Reporting

What we have achieved (I)

Month 1–3: Planning and Resource Allocation

Management Structure and dynamics

Steering committee

Executive Committee

Advisory Board

Planning and resource allocation
(February)

What we have achieved (II)

Month 3-6: Review of Current Practices

Analysis of the current system

Researchers' perceptions

ReAss best practices identified

Analysis of the current system

A well-developed system during the last 10 years

Institutional evaluations follow a three-year cycle

Unified evaluation criteria across several faculties (SSH; Blanquerna)

Aimed to stimulate research activity, support career development strategies, and maintain quality standards required by external agencies.

Evaluation Criteria

Productivity (60%): Impact-factor publications (JCR, SJR), books or chapters (SPI), dissemination activities (conference presentations, peer review, editorial boards), and contributions like doctoral supervision and patents.

Projects (35%): Leadership or participation in competitive and non-competitive projects, with some recognition also given to unsuccessful competitive proposals.

Other merits (5%): Research group leadership and research stays (minimum one month).

Results of the last round of RA

In the latest call, 80 researchers participated, with 20% exempt due to external evaluation credentials. Of the remaining 64, 43% received a “very favorable” evaluation, 42% “favorable,” and 14% “unfavorable.”

Only faculty members with recognized research time were required to participate.

A differentiated scoring threshold was applied based on contract type.

Feedback

Overall (very favorable, favorable, or not favorable)

Score out of 100

Average and score range for their academic category

The scoring table for each evaluation parameter

Researchers' perceptions (N = 26)

Strengths

- Standardisation of criteria
- Acknowledgement and follow-up
- Formative purpose

Weaknesses

- Heavy Dependence on Quantitative Indicators
- Limited diversification of criteria (e.g., knowledge transference, social impact, or interdisciplinarity).
- Lacks support and resources (low impact)

Threats

- Resistance to Reform
- Credibility Gaps (perceived lack objectivity)
- Potential overload and bureaucracy

Opportunities

- Qualitative, flexible and personalised benchmarking
- Innovation and Inclusion
- Interdisciplinary and Societal Impact Recognition

What we have achieved (II)

Month 5-6: Development of New Criteria

SWOT

Main
Challenges

New criteria
development

SWOT Analysis of Current Research Assessment Practices

Strengths

- Institutionalization and Continuity
- Structured and Transparent Procedures
- Integration of Quality Assurance Structures
- Efforts Towards Unity and Reflection
- Formative aim of the research evaluation

Weaknesses

- Heavy Dependence on Quantitative Indicators
- Limited Recognition of Diverse Contributions
- Rigid Top-Down Scoring Model
- Partial Coverage
- Limited Peer Involvement and Reflective Dialogue

Threats

- Resistance to Reform
- Credibility Gaps (perceived lack objectivity)
- Loss of Benchmarking Ease
- Potential overload for evaluators

Opportunities

- Fostering Researcher Development (profiles)
- Innovation and Inclusion
- Interdisciplinary and Societal Impact Recognition

New criteria: ReAss dimensions of change

Broaden the conceptualization of Research Quality

Problematization of the research assessment and research quality concepts

Including **community engagement, open science, interdisciplinary work, and knowledge transfer.**

Embed Peer Review and Narrative Assessment

Procedures and tools for qualitative, peer-based evaluation: **narrative CVs or portfolios tailored to Blanquerna's research fields.**

Ensure researcher development and inclusivity Across Career Stages

Flexible, transparent benchmarks that consider researcher development (ECR; Alt careers).

Address the tension between researcher teamwork and individual development

Enhance Reflexivity and Transparency

Ensure **formative feedback**, dialogic assessment practices

Foster Researcher Engagement and Co-Creation

Sustain **ongoing consultation** and training with researchers to **co-create** the new criteria

Discuss the Role of Evaluation in Career Progression

Start the discussion regarding how assessment outcomes influence **recognition, research time allocation, and promotion** within a framework consistent with CoARA

New criteria: ReAss dimensions of change

Align Individual and Group-Based Assessment to Support Sustainable Research Environments

Addressing the tension between individual performance evaluation and collective research practices by recognising collaborative roles, team science, and shared responsibility for research quality, with the aim of fostering resilient and sustainable research ecosystems.

Proposta CV Narratiu

1. Dades personals

- Nom i cognoms:
- Posició actual i unitat acadèmica:
- ORCID i altres identificadors:
- Mètriques alternatives:

(Indicar només les dades necessàries per identificar-te en l'àmbit de la recerca; evita dades personals no rellevants)

2. Resum de trajectòria (màx. 200 paraules)

(Explica breument la teva trajectòria investigadora: línies principals, context, mobilitat, etapes destacades. Pots incloure períodes de pausa o canvi de sector si vols que es tinguin en compte.)

3. Contribucions principals (estructura modular)

Mòdul 1. Generació de coneixement

(Describeu com has contribuït a generar nous coneixements, idees, eines, metodologies. Pots incloure publicacions clau, conjunts de dades, software, patents, informes de política, etc. Explica per què són importants i el teu rol específic. Open Access. Escalabilidad) (màxim XX paraules)

Mòdul 2. Desenvolupament de xarxes, formació investigadors i relacions de treball

(Explica com has format, mentorat o liderat equips i estudiants. Pots descriure experiències de supervisió, co-creació d'equips, lideratge de projectes, polítiques inclusives. Explica també la teva contribució i el teu rol dins l'equip de recerca. Capacitat de treballar inter i transdisciplinarietat) (màxim XX paraules)

Mòdul 3. Contribucions a la comunitat científica i d'innovació

(Participació en xarxes, comitès, revisió editorial, Dades obertes obertura de dades, millora de la cultura de recerca, igualtat i diversitat. Mostra l'impacte i el context. Congressos. Altmetrics.) (màxim XX paraules)

Mòdul 4. Contribucions a la societat i usuaris més amplis

(Transferència de coneixement, col·laboració amb institucions públiques/privades, participació en processos polítics, divulgació científica. Explica els canvis que ha generat la teva aportació. Ciència ciutadana. Iniciatives de co-creació.) (màxim XX paraules)

4. LListat contribucions principals

(Pots afegir una taula amb fins a 10 resultats clau: referència completa, descripció del teu rol i enllaç, identificar o DOI. Aquest model és inspirat en el format d'AGAUR i NWO.) Pots incloure referència de projectes competitiu, articles indexats, informes de polítiques públiques, conferències rellevants, patents, etc.

Tirol i dades	Contribució	Enllaç/ DOI
Exemple: Article XX	aig dirigir l'estudi i vaig dissenyar la metodologia; impacte en polítiques d'avaluació	https://doi.org/...

5. Valoració de la trajectòria

(Quines són les teves motivacions, valors i objectius en l'àmbit de la recerca? Per què és rellevant la teva trajectòria en el nostre context? Quines àrees t'interessa millorar/ potenciar? Quina és la teva estratègia per als propers 3-4 anys per afavorir el teu creixement professional i el desenvolupament de la teva recerca? Com s'emmarca aquesta estratègia en el desenvolupament de l'equip de recerca?)

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Thank you for your attention

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